

COMPONENT ACIDS OF INDIAN ELASMOBRANCH LIVER OILS

BY G. G. KAMATH AND N. G. MAGAR

DEPARTMENT OF BIOCHEMISTRY, INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY-1

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Carcharias limbatus (Pisori) and *Cestracion blochii* (Kan-Mushi) liver oils have been fractionated by low temperature crystallisation, fractional distillation of methyl esters and alkali isomerisation of unsaturated fractions for their component fatty acids.

C. limbatus liver oil contains 33.8% saturated and 66.2% unsaturated acids. *C. blochii* contains 25.5% saturated and 74.5% unsaturated acids. In both oils C_{18} acids are predominant. Next to C_{18} acids are C_{20} acids in *C. limbatus* and C_{18} monoethenoid acid in *C. blochii*.

It has been shown that elasmobranch fish liver oils exist in diversified compositions^{1,2}. To confirm the above findings the present investigation on the liver oils from *Carcharias limbatus* and *Cestracion blochii*, caught off Bombay Coast, was undertaken. The local names for these are 'Pisori' and 'Kan-Mushi' respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fresh samples of livers from the identified species were cooked in an autoclave for 15 minutes at 15 lbs. pressure (p.s.i.) with one third its weight of water. The livers yielded 40-50% oil. This was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

After removing the unsaponifiable matter by extraction with ether after saponifying the oil with alcoholic potash, the mixed fatty acids were liberated by acidifying with HCl and then extracted with ethyl ether³. The fatty acids were resolved into groups with differing mean unsaturation, by adopting the low-temperature separation scheme of Gupta and Hilditch⁴.

Octadecadienoic and octadecatrienoic acids were estimated in the unsaturated groups by alkali isomerisation in ethyleneglycol, as recommended by Hilditch, Morton and Riley⁵, and other polyunsaturated acids according to Herb *et al*⁶. The methyl esters of less unsaturated fatty acids were distilled under vacuum using an E.H.P. column designed by Longenecker⁷. Only alkali isomerisation data have been relied upon for the highly unsaturated fatty acid fractions.

Saponification equivalent (S.E.) and iodine value (I.V.) were determined according to the American Oil Chemists Society (Hand-book of

Official and Tentative methods, 1951) and the calculations, based on the recommendations of Hilditch³.

C. limbatus liver oil.—The oil (133.4 g. S.E. 284.7 ; I.V. 112.4) gave 5.65 g. unsaponifiables and 121.0 g. fatty acids (S.E. 280.1, I.V. 109.7). The mixed fatty acids (118 g.) were subjected to low-temperature separations using 10% w/v solution. The results are shown in Table I. Methyl ester fractionation data for groups A, B and C are presented in Table II. Alkali-isomerisation data are recorded in Table III. The component fatty acids present in A, B, C and D groups and in whole fat were calculated from these data, and the results are presented in Table IV.

TABLE I

Low-temperature separation of fatty acids.

Description	Fraction.	<i>C. limbatus</i> .				<i>Cestracion blochii</i> .				
		Amount.	I.V.	S.E.	Fraction.	Amount.	I.V.	S.E.		
1. -30°; ether-insoluble	A	38.8 g.	32.9%	17.7	260.0	A'	34.5 g.	34.5%	44.5	270.2
2. -30°; ether-soluble ; -55°, acetone-insoluble	B	19.2	16.3	87.6	280.0	B'	33.5	33.5	130.8	272.4
3. -55°; acetone-soluble	...	...	...	...	...	C'	32.0	32.0	237.2	285.5
4. -55°; acetone-soluble ; -70°, acetone-insoluble	C	17.8	15.1	126.6	291.8	—	—	—	—	—
5. -70°; acetone-soluble	D	42.2	35.7	19 ^c .6	291.0	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE II

Methyl ester fractionation of A, B and C acids in C. limbatus.

Methyl esters of A.				Methyl esters of B.				Methyl esters of C.			
No. *	Wt.	S.E.	I.V.	No.	Wt.	S.E.	I.V.	No.	Wt.	S.E.	I.V.
A ₁	3.53 g.	257.8	5.1	B ₁	1.71	249.0	26.0	C ₁	1.62	283.4	53.9
A ₂	3.44	265.1	7.2	B ₂	2.36	263.8	58.9	C ₂	1.95	289.6	75.1
A ₃	4.36.	266.3	3.7*	B ₃	2.29	275.7	92.2	C ₃	1.82	294.7	80.3
A ₄	4.48	268.5	4.0	B ₄	2.27	285.1	89.1	C ₄	5.49	306.6*	164.5*
A ₅	4.89	274.9	13.8	B ₅	5.28	318.0*	107.0*				
A ₆	3.90	285.9	14.8								
A ₇	3.03	292.0	18.4								
A ₈	1.26	294.3	19.4.								
A ₉	7.71	300.4*	37.3*								

*Values for the esters freed from unsaponifiables.

TABLE III

Alkali isomerisation data for unsaturated fractions.

Conditions.	Fraction.	Octadeca- dienoic.	Octadeca- trienoic.	Eicosa- tetraenoic.	Docosa- pentaenoic (C ₂₂ - 10H)
(i) 7.5 g. KOH-gly- col; 170° for 15 mins. (ethanol)	C	...	23.81%	Present	Present
	D	...	40.78	"	"
	B'	...	14.21	"	"
	C'	...	52.75	"	"
(ii) 7.5 g. KOH-gly- col; 180° for 10 mins. (ethanol)	C ^o	7.00%	...	...	...
	D	1.37	...	...	...
	B'	1.02	...	...	...
	C'	Absent	...	...	...
(iii) 21% KOH-glycol; 180° for 15 mins. (methanol)	C	...	...	1.91%	2.63%
	D	...	...	8.10	3.92
	B'	...	...	1.77	2.52
	C'	...	...	7.85	10.83

TABLE IV

Component acids of C. limbatus liver oil.

	Group A (wt.%).	Group B (wt.%).	Group C (wt.%).	Group D (wt.%).	Wt.%. Total	Mol.%. Total
Saturated :						
Myristic	2.29	1.30	...	...	3.59	4.37
Palmitic	15.97	1.26	0.56	...	17.79	19.29
Stearic	8.43	...	0.81	...	9.24	9.03
Arachidic	0.36	...	2.85	...	3.21	2.85
Unsaturated :						
C ₁₄ (-2H)	0.08	0.57	...	...	0.65	0.80
C ₁₆ (-2H)	1.40	4.60	1.08	...	7.08	7.74
C ₁₈ (-2H)	3.84	2.37	4.58	6.46	17.25	16.97
(-4H)	...	0.43	1.03	0.49	1.95	1.93
(-6H)	...	0.68	3.52	14.56	18.76	18.73
C ₂₀ (-2H)	0.51	5.01	...	9.92	15.44	13.82
(-8H)	...	0.06	0.28	2.90	3.24	2.96
C ₂₂ (-10H)	...	...	0.38	1.42	1.80	1.51
Total	32.98	16.28	15.09	35.75	100.00	100.00

Cestacion blochii liver oil.—The oil (144.0 g., S.E. 3128; I.V. 146.5) gave 11.92 g. unsaponifiable matter and 121.0 g. mixed fatty acids (S.E. 280.5, I. V. 137.4). The results of low-temperature separations using 100 g. mixed fatty acids are shown in Table I. Other relevant data are presented in Tables III, V and VI.

TABLE V
Methyl ester fractionation of 'A' and 'B' acids of (*Cestracion blochii*).

No.	Methyl esters of A'			No.	Methyl esters of B'		
	Amount.	S.E.	I.V.		Amount.	S.E.	I.V.
A ₁	3.40 g.	264.9	8.5	B ₁	2.63 g.	250.0	27.2
A ₂	4.17	274.9	26.9	B ₂	3.47	270.7	68.4
A ₃	4.01	277.2	37.6	B ₃	3.11	282.9	79.6
A ₄	3.85	279.9	42.2	B ₄	3.17	291.6	110.7
A ₅	4.03	294.6	47.5	B ₅	2.65	294.9	132.8
A ₆	3.57	302.1	61.7	B ₆	2.53	301.9	234.0
A ₇	3.22	315.4*	82.2*	B ₇	6.03	310.9*	179.8*

* Values for the esters freed from unsaponifiables.

TABLE VI
Component acids of *Cestracion blochii* liver oil.

	Group A'	Group B'	Group C'	Total	
	(wt. %).	(wt. %).	(wt. %).	Wt. %	Mol. %
Saturated :					
Myristic	0.68	1.79	...	2.47	3.0
Palmitic	10.74	2.76	...	13.50	14.6
Stearic	5.82	1.32	...	7.14	7.0
Arachidic	0.27	2.08	...	2.35	2.1
Unsaturated :					
C ₁₄ (-2H)	0.05	0.62	...	0.67	0.8
C ₁₆ (-2H)	4.35	5.66	...	10.01	10.9
C ₁₈ (-2H)	8.85	8.69	9.14	26.68	26.2
(-4H)	...	0.40	...	0.40	0.4
(-6H)	...	7.07	16.88	23.95	23.8
C ₂₀ (-2H)	3.74	0.71	...	4.45	4.0
(-8H)	...	0.59	2.51	3.10	2.8
C ₂₂ (-10H)	...	1.81	3.47	5.28	4.4
C ₂₄ (-12H)	...	...	Traces	Traces	...
Total	34.50	33.50	32.00	100.00	100.00

DISCUSSION

In *C. limbatu*s liver oil, 33.82% acids are saturated, 66.17% being unsaturated. Palmitic acid is the most predominant of the saturated acids, followed by stearic acid.* Only small amounts of myristic and arachidic acids are present. The C₁₈ series of acids dominate the unsaturated group with 37.96%. This is followed by 16.68% C₂₀ acids and 7.08% palmitoleic acid. C₁₄ and C₂₂ acids are present in only small amounts.

In *Cestracion blochii* liver oil, saturated acids comprise only 25.5% of the total acids. This was expected from the relatively high iodide value of the oil. Palmitic acid is once again seen to be the major component of the saturated acids. 51.0% of the total acids is on the C₁₈ unsaturated series. Palmitoleic acid is next with 10.0%. C₂₀ and C₂₂ acids are present only in small proportions.

For comparison, the component fatty acids of these two oils are presented in Table VII along with the two oils analysed previously⁸.

TABLE VII
Component fatty acids of elasmobranch liver oils (wt %)

	<i>Galeocerdo tigrinus</i> .	<i>C. melanopterus</i> .	<i>C. limbatus</i> .	<i>Cestracion blochii</i>
Saturated :				
Myristic	0.9	6.1	3.6	2.5
Palmitic	21.6	16.9	17.8	13.5
Stearic	6.3	3.7	9.2	7.1
Arachidic	6.4	1.1	3.2	2.4
Unsaturated :				
C ₁₄ (-2H)	—	1.3	0.6	0.7
C ₁₆ (-2H)	7.1	17.2	7.1	10.0
C ₁₈ (-2H)	10.9	23.4	17.3	26.7
(-4H)	0.4	7.0	2.0	0.4
(-6H)	2.4	17.5	18.8	23.9
C ₂₀ (-2H)	19.3	—	15.4	4.4
(-8H)	1.7	2.7	3.2	3.1
(-10H)	—	1.5	—	—
C ₂₂ (-2H)	22.7	—	—	—
(-10H)	0.3	1.5	1.8 ⁸	5.3
(-12H)	—	0.1 (?)	—	—

It can be seen from Table VII that *G. tigrinus* oil differs from the other oils in having higher proportions of C₂₀ and C₂₂ acids. In other samples, the major component acids are of the C₁₈ series. Palmitic acid is the predominating saturated acid present in all the samples analysed. *C. limbatus* liver oil has 18% C₂₀ acids and is thus intermediate between *C. melanopterus* having increased proportion of C₁₈ acids and *G. tigrinus* with high amounts of C₂₂ acids.

Only the *G. tigrinus* sample resembles the samples analysed by Pathak *et al.*¹ in having higher proportions of C₂₀ and C₂₂ acids. There is no similarity between the other samples analysed in the present study with any of those analysed by Pathak *et al.*

Lovern⁹ has shown that certain elasmobranch fish fats evinced a regular abnormality in the proportion of their various fatty acids, e.g. acids of lower molecular weight are either suppressed or increased in amount with the corresponding increase or decrease of the higher acids. The findings of the present study are in conformity with these observations. The presence of arachidic acid is significant. It is usually not ingested by the elasmobranch fish and is suggestive of a hydrogenation process. Lovern has suggested the possibility of an enzymic reversible hydrogenation-dehydrogenation process in fish. This possibly accounts for the wide variation in the saturations of the fish-liver oils analysed.

The present study thus establishes the existence of diversified compositions in the liver oils of *Elasmobranchii*.

R E F E R E N C E S

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